

Supplemental Material

- Supplemental Methods: Detailed description of modeling 2
- Supplemental Tables..... 5
 - Supplemental Table S1: Model parameter estimates of mixed-effect regression analysis (base model without covariates)..... 5
 - Supplemental Table S2: Summary of mono-variate covariate analysis..... 6
 - Supplemental Table S3: Model parameter estimates of final covariate models 7
- Supplemental Figures 8
 - Supplemental Figure S1: Comparison of osmolality measurements from the two different study centers using the same osmometer (Perth and Basel)..... 8
 - Supplemental Figure S2: Model-predicted individual profiles (deterministic simulations): patients with newly diagnosed type 1 diabetes (T1D) versus patients with known T1D versus statistical category attributed by mixture model 9

Supplemental Methods: Detailed description of modeling

Modeling of kinetics and dynamics

The temporal course of osmolality and copeptin (kinetics), as well as the relationship between osmolality and copeptin (dynamics), were characterized using nonlinear mixed-effect regression modelling in Monolix® (version 2018R2, Antony, France: Lixoft SAS, 2018). This method simultaneously estimates mean population and individual model parameters, quantifies associated between-subject variability (BSV), and allows characterizing both overall mean and individual profiles.

Overall characterization by base model

Several structural models were considered to describe the temporal course of copeptin and osmolality over time (kinetics: mono-/bi-exponential decline models) and the correlation between osmolality and copeptin (dynamics: log-linear, exponential, logistic Emax-models).

BSV of structural model parameters was assumed to be log-normally distributed:

$$\log(P_i) = \log(P_{pop}) + \eta_i \equiv P_i = P_{pop} \cdot e^{\eta_i} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where P_i is the individual parameter, P_{pop} the population parameter, and η_i the individual normally distributed random effect.

Residual intra-individual variability was modelled using a proportional error model:

$$Obs_{i,j} = Pred_{i,j} \cdot (1 + \varepsilon_{i,j}) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where $Obs_{i,j} / Pred_{i,j}$ is the j^{th} observation/prediction of i^{th} individual, and $\varepsilon_{i,j}$ the residual error.

Covariate analysis

The association between individual model parameter estimates and the following covariates was assessed: mild versus moderate-severe DKA (classified following graphical investigation), known versus newly diagnosed T1D, gender, age and weight. Associations were first screened

by analysis of variance (ANOVA) for categorical variables and by Pearson's correlation test for continuous variables. All variables with a p-value <0.15 were subsequently tested as covariates in mono-variate regression analysis. All covariates leading to a significant improvement in model fit based on the likelihood ratio test (LRT, p <0.05) were then combined in a multivariate model, while considering their ability to explain (i.e. reduce) inter-individual variability (BSV expressed as coefficient of variation, CV%) (Eq. 3).

$$CV_{explained}[\%] = \frac{CV_{cov} - CV_{base}}{CV_{base}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where $CV_{explained}$ is the explained BSV, CV_{cov} : BSV of the covariate model and CV_{base} : BSV of the base model.

An additional analysis was performed to further explain the large BSV in copeptin kinetics observed, irrespective of the covariates mentioned previously. The presence of two types of kinetic profiles was observed: high initial values with steep decline, low initial value with flat decline. Those profiles were characterized using a mixture model, i.e. statistical classification of patients into two kinetic groups as latent variable, with separate parameter estimates.

Model evaluation

Model selection was guided by comparison of the likelihood-based Akaike information criterion (AIC) (base model) and -2xlog-likelihood (nested covariate models), precision of parameter estimates (target <40%) and goodness-of-fit plots (residual diagnostics, individual random effects versus covariates, simulation based visual predictive check VPC). The VPC is a graphical assessment comparing empirical percentiles and model-predicted percentiles (based on 500 simulations).

Sensitivity analyses

Two sensitivity analyses were performed to assess potential changes in model parameter estimates. Both the final osmolality kinetic and dynamic model were re-fitted (1) to the full dataset, i.e. including the previously excluded, considered erroneous, osmolality

measurements, and (2) to a reduced data set comprising only the first 24h, since the first 24h are of highest clinical relevance and the observed transient increase of osmolality between 24h-72h was not perfectly captured by the osmolality kinetic model.

In a third sensitivity analysis, a potential study centre effect was investigated as covariate in the osmolality kinetic model, to exclude potential systematic measurement differences despite use of the same osmometer in both study centers.

Illustration of model predictions

Model predictions were illustrated by deterministic (individual profiles according to individual parameter estimates) and stochastic simulations (median profile with 5th and 95th percentiles according to estimated BSV and covariance, based on n=1000 simulated individual parameter combinations).

Supplemental Tables

Supplemental Table S1: Model parameter estimates of mixed-effect regression analysis

(base model without covariates).

(A) Kinetic copeptin / osmolality models. Those models describe the concentration C at time t using the following structural relationship:

$$C(t) = (C_0 - C_{lim}) \cdot e^{-k \cdot t} + C_{lim}, \text{ where:}$$

C_0 : Initial concentration at time $t=0$

k : recovery rate

$t_{1/2}$: derived 50% recovery time, calculated as: $t_{1/2} = \ln(2)/k$

C_{lim} : asymptotic concentration over time

Parameter	Value	(CI 95%)	CV [%]	(%RSE)
Copeptin kinetics				
C_0 [pmol/L]	95.2	(55-136)	158*	(14)
k [h ⁻¹]	0.10	(0.06-0.13)	114*	(15)
→ corresponding $t_{1/2}$ [h]	7.1	(5.1-11.5)		
C_{lim} [pmol/L]	9.7	(8.1-11.4)	31	(27)
residual error [%]	9.3			(4.8)
Osmolality kinetics				
C_0 [mOsm/kg]	321	(315-327)	4.4	(15)
k [h ⁻¹]	0.16	(0.11-0.21)	64	(22)
→ corresponding $t_{1/2}$ [h]	4.3	(3.0-5.6)		
C_{lim} [mOsm/kg]	294	(292-296)	1.0	(27)
residual error [%]	0.31			(4.7)

RSE: relative standard error. CV: Inter-individual variability expressed as coefficient of variation: $CV\% = \sqrt{e^{\omega^2} - 1} \cdot 100\%$, where ω is the estimated standard-deviation of individual random effects (η). *In the copeptin model, a correlation of 0.745 between ω_{C_0} and ω_k was additionally estimated.

(B) Dynamic relationship between osmolality and copeptin. This model described the copeptin concentration C at given osmolality osm using the following structural relationship:

$$C(osm) = C_{280} \cdot e^{slope \cdot (osm - 280)}, \text{ where:}$$

C_{280} : baseline copeptin concentration at osmolality of 280 mOsm/kg

slope: rate of exponential increase

C_2 : derived osmolality interval for which copeptin doubles, calculated as: $C_2 = \ln(2)/slope$

Parameter	Value	(CI 95%)	CV [%]	(%RSE)
C_{280} [pmol/L]	9.8	(7.3-12.3)	48	(23)
slope [kg/mOsm]	0.04	(0.03-0.06)	59	(32)
→ corresponding C_2	15.6	(10.3-20.9)		
residual error [%]	16.2			(5.0)

RSE: relative standard error. CV: Inter-individual variability expressed as coefficient of variation: $CV\% = \varepsilon = \sqrt{e^{\omega^2} - 1} \cdot 100\%$

Supplemental Table S2: Summary of mono-variate covariate analysis.

All covariates (x) were included following the following default linear relationship with log-transformed parameters, categorical variables were coded as dummy variables (0/1):

$$\ln(P_{pop}) = \ln(P_{ref}) + \beta \cdot x \equiv P_{ref} \cdot e^{\beta \cdot x}, \text{ where}$$

- P_{pop} : typical population parameter for a given covariate x
 P_{ref} : typical population parameter for reference covariate x=0
 β : regression coefficient

	P _{ref} (%RSE)		β (%RSE)		CV[%] (%RSE)		P-value*
Copeptin kinetics							
Is C ₀ influenced by							
...newly diagnosed T1D ?	270	(33)	-1.41	(27)	106	(15)	0.0008
...moderate-severe DKA ?	32.2	(59)	1.24	(51)	130	(14)	0.044
Is k influenced by?							
...newly diagnosed T1D ?	0.26	(22)	-1.25	(22)	65	(17)	0.0001
Is C _{lim} influenced by							
...age?	15.3	(21)	-0.04	(49)	22	(26)	0.057
Osmolality kinetics							
Is C ₀ influenced by							
... newly diagnosed T1D?	329	(2)	-0.04	(53)	4.1	(15)	0.054
Is k influenced by							
...moderate-severe DKA?	0.73	(40)	-1.65	(25)	39	(26)	0.001
Is C _{lim} influenced by							
...male?	293	(0.4)	0.01	(82)	0.8	(30)	0.14
...weight?	290	(0.8)	3.0E-04	(53)	0.8	(30)	0.083
...age?	290	(1.0)	1.2E-03	(70)	0.9	(29)	0.084
Dynamic relationship							
Is slope influenced by							
...newly diagnosed T1D?	0.067	(17)	-0.54	(44)	44	(25)	0.116
...moderate-severe DKA?	0.013	(60)	1.35	(45)	42	(23)	0.040
Is C ₂₈₀ influenced by							
...newly diagnosed T1D	5.7	(20)	0.75	(31)	41	(41)	0.0016

*likelihood ratio test. RSE: relative standard error. CV: Inter-individual variability expressed as coefficient of variation: CV% = $\sqrt{e^{\omega^2} - 1} \cdot 100\%$, where ω is the estimated standard-deviation of individual random effects (η_i) of the respective parameter. T1D: type 1 diabetes; DKA: diabetic ketoacidosis

Supplemental Table S3: Model parameter estimates of final covariate models. For structural model equations and covariate relationships: see Supplemental Tables S2-3.

(A) T1D covariate models

Parameter	Value	(%RSE)	CV[%]	(%RSE)	Δ CV[%]
Copeptin kinetics					
$C_{0,ref} = C_{0, known T1D}$ [pmol/L]	282	(32)	103	(15)	-35
$\beta_{C_{0,newly diagnosed T1D}}$	-1.51	(25)			
→ $C_{0, newly diagnosed}$ [pmol/L]	62.3				
$k_{ref} = k_{known T1D}$ [h ⁻¹]	0.27	(22)	64	(18)	-44
→ $t_{1/2 known T1D}$ [h]	2.5				
$\beta_{k,newly diagnosed T1D}$	-1.34	(21)			
→ $t_{1/2 newly diagnosed T1D}$ [h]	9.6				
C_{lim} [pmol/L]	9.9	(8)	22	(39)	-29
residual error [%]	9.4	(5)			
Copeptin dynamics					
$C_{280,ref} = C_{280, known T1D}$ [pmol/L]	5.7	(20)	41	(28)	-15
$\beta_{C_{280, newly diagnosed T1D}}$	0.75	(31)			
→ $C_{280, newly diagnosed}$ [pmol/L]	12.0				
<i>slope</i> [mOsm/kg ⁻¹]	0.04	(17)	70	(25)	+19
→ C_2 [mOsm/kg]	16.2				
residual error [%]	16	(5)			

RSE: relative standard error. CV: Inter-individual variability expressed as coefficient of variation: $CV\% = \sqrt{e^{\omega^2} - 1} \cdot 100\%$, where ω is the estimated standard-deviation of individual random effects (η_i) of the respective parameter. T1D: type 1 diabetes.

(B) Mixture models: statistically assigned category $x=0$ (reference, corresponding to “steep” copeptin decline profile) or $x=1$ (“flat” copeptin decline profile)

Parameter	Value	(%RSE)	CV[%]	(%RSE)	Δ CV[%]
Copeptin kinetics					
$C_{0,ref}$ [pmol/L]	285	(15)	47	(17)	-70
$\beta_{C_{0,x=1}}$	-2.1	(9.5)			
→ $C_{0,x=1}$	35				
k_{ref} [h ⁻¹]	0.22	(15)	54	(18)	-53
→ $t_{1/2,ref}$ [h]	3.1				
$\beta_{k,x=1}$	-1.5	(15)			
→ $t_{1/2,x=1}$ [h]	14.4				
C_{lim} [pmol/L]	9.7	(7)	27	(26)	-13
proportion $x=0$	0.48	(fixed)			
residual error [%]	9.1	(5)			
Copeptin dynamics					
$C_{280,ref}$ [pmol/L]	6.5	(17)	47	(19)	-2
$\beta_{C_{280,x=1}}$	0.8	(30)			
→ $C_{280,x=1}$ [pmol/L]	14.1				
<i>Slope</i> _{ref} [mOsm/kg ⁻¹]	0.08	(10)	30	(36)	-49
→ $C_{2,ref}$ [mOsm/kg]	8.9				
$\beta_{slope,x=1}$	-1.34	(22)			
→ $C_{2,x=1}$ [mOsm/kg]	34.1				
residual error [%]	15.7	(5)			

(C) DKA covariate model

Parameter	Value	(%RSE)	CV[%]	(%RSE)	Δ CV[%]
Osmolality kinetics					
C_0 [pmol/L]	321	(0.98)	4.7	(15)	+7
$k_{ref} = k_{mild DKA}$ [h ⁻¹]	0.73	(40)	39	(26)	-39
→ $t_{1/2 mild DKA}$ [h]	0.95				
$\beta_{k, moderate-severe DKA}$	-1.65	(25)			
→ $t_{1/2 moderate-severe DKA}$ [h]	5.0				
C_{lim} [pmol/L]	294	(0.29)	1.1	(22)	+10
residual error [%]	0.3	(4.7)			

Supplemental Figures

Supplemental Figure S1: Comparison of osmolality measurements from the two different study centers using the same osmometer (Perth and Basel). In line with this visual assessment, no center effect could be identified in the sensitivity analysis. *Dots*: measurements. *Lines*: non-parametric regression line (loess).

Supplemental Figure S2: Model-predicted individual profiles (deterministic simulations): patients with newly diagnosed type 1 diabetes (T1D) versus patients with known T1D versus statistical category attributed by mixture model (differentiated by different line types). **A:** copeptin kinetics, **B:** osmolality kinetics, **C/D:** dynamic relationship between osmolality and copeptin on semi-log scale (C) and normal scale (D). *Solid line:* indicates patients statistically attributed to a group of patients with similar “steep copeptin decline” kinetics (highly correlating with rather high initial copeptin values >90 pmol/L). *Dashed line:* patients statistically attributed to a group of patients with similar “flat copeptin decline” kinetics (highly correlating with rather low initial copeptin values <90 pmol/L).